

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SKIN GEL CONTAINING LIQUORICE, PAPAYA AND BUTTERFLY PEA FLOWER EXTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a polyherbal topical gel containing Papaya, Butterfly pea flower, and Liquorice for potential skincare applications. Herbal gels have gained increasing attention in cosmetic and dermatological formulations due to their natural origin, better skin compatibility, and lower risk of adverse effects. The selected herbal ingredients were chosen for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, skin-brightening, and moisturizing properties. Papaya extract was used for enzymatic exfoliation and depigmentation, butterfly pea flower for antioxidant and anti-aging activity, and liquorice for skin soothing and pigmentation control. The extracts were prepared individually using suitable maceration techniques and incorporated into a gel base formulated with natural gelling agents, namely Gum Katira and flaxseed mucilage. Four formulations (F1–F4) were

prepared by varying the concentrations of Gum Katira and flaxseed mucilage while keeping the concentration of herbal extracts constant. The prepared gels were evaluated for physicochemical parameters including color, odor, homogeneity, pH, consistency, spreadability, viscosity, irritancy, after-feel, ease of removal, and stability. All formulations showed satisfactory organoleptic and physicochemical properties with smooth texture, uniform appearance, pleasant odor, and good homogeneity. The pH of all formulations ranged from 6.0 to 6.53, indicating compatibility with skin. Among the formulations, **F2** showed optimum consistency, desirable appearance, and acceptable pH, suggesting better suitability

for topical application. The results indicate that the developed herbal gel possesses promising characteristics as a natural topical formulation for skincare, with potential applications in hydration, soothing, anti-acne, and skin-brightening treatments.

KEYWORDS: Herbal gel, Herbal skincare, *Carica papaya*, *Clitoria ternatea*, *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, Gum Katira, Flaxseed mucilage, Topical gel, Natural gelling agents.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal Gels

Skincare plays an important role in maintaining the health and appearance of both facial and body skin. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in herbal formulations because of their effectiveness and lower risk of side effects. Herbal cosmetic products, such as face washes, creams, shampoos, soaps, conditioners, and gels, are commonly used by people as they are mainly derived from natural plant sources. These products are generally regarded as safe since they contain botanical ingredients that offer therapeutic benefits with minimal adverse reactions.

Herbal gels are a type of natural skincare product that combine plant extracts with a gel base to provide hydration, nourishment, and protection to the skin. These formulations help in soothing, calming, and revitalizing the skin, leading to a healthy and glowing appearance. The increasing preference for herbal gels is mainly due to their high efficiency and reduced chances of causing irritation.

These gels are widely known for their healing properties and adaptability in skincare. They are especially suitable for sensitive skin because they do not contain harsh chemicals. Ingredients like aloe vera, neem, basil, and chamomile have anti-inflammatory and soothing effects, which help reduce redness and irritation. In addition, herbal gels produce a cooling effect, making them useful in treating sunburn, rashes, and minor skin problems.

Moreover, herbal gels moisturize the skin effectively without leaving a greasy residue, making them ideal for oily skin types. Some herbal formulations, such as tea tree gel, also have antibacterial properties that help manage acne by preventing the growth of acne-causing bacteria. Therefore, herbal gels serve as a natural and effective alternative in contemporary skincare product.

Fig. 1: Herbal gel.

Ideal Properties of a Herbal Gel

- **Skin-Friendly:** Mild and non-irritating, making it appropriate for sensitive skin.
- **Moisturizing:** Includes humectants that help retain moisture and keep the skin soft and supple
- **Calming Effect:** Reduces inflammation and redness due to the presence of active plant constituents.
- **Rich in Antioxidants:** Shields the skin from oxidative damage and environmental stress.
- **Quick Absorption:** Readily penetrates the skin without leaving an oily or sticky feel.
- **Pleasant Aroma:** Contains natural fragrances that offer a soothing and refreshing sensation.
- **Versatile Use:** Effective in managing multiple skin concerns such as dryness, acne, and irritation.

Uses

- Helps reduce inflammation and skin irritation due to its natural anti-inflammatory components
- Soothes common skin issues like acne, redness, and itching
- Offers relief for sunburn, as well as minor cuts and scrapes
- Keeps the skin well-hydrated and improves softness and smoothness
- Aids in retaining moisture, which can help minimize the appearance of fine lines and wrinkles
- Maintains prolonged hydration, even in dry conditions

Advantages

- Safe to use and well-tolerated by the skin due to its natural compatibility.
- Improves absorption of active ingredients into the skin.
- Provides a cooling sensation that helps soothe and calm the skin.

- Has a lightweight, non-oily texture that feels comfortable on application.
- Helps maintain skin hydration by retaining moisture.
- Environmentally friendly and made from sustainable resources.

Disadvantages

- May lead to increased sensitivity to sunlight in certain individuals.
- Susceptible to microbial contamination during storage or use.
- Difficult to maintain precise dosage levels.
- Excessive use can result in skin irritation or allergic reactions.
- Some active compounds show limited ability to penetrate the skin.
- Possibility of incompatibility between different ingredients.

Acne

Acne is a chronic and common disorder of the pilosebaceous units of the skin that occurs due to abnormal sebaceous gland activity within hair follicles. It is most commonly seen among adolescents and young adults, particularly individuals between 18 and 25 years of age. Acne vulgaris is characterized by seborrhea, comedone formation, inflammatory lesions, and the presence of microorganisms such as *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* within the follicular canal along with excessive sebum production. It is considered one of the most prevalent skin disorders worldwide and affects individuals of all races, with nearly 95% of boys and 83% of girls experiencing acne during adolescence. In males, acne generally resolves during early adulthood, although approximately 5% of men continue to have acne at 25 years of age. In females, acne may persist into adulthood, affecting around 12% of women at 25 years and about 5% even at 45 years of age. Acne vulgaris has a multifactorial etiology in which genetic predisposition plays a significant role. The condition develops through the interaction of several factors, including follicular epidermal hyperproliferation leading to blockage of follicles, excessive sebum secretion, colonization and activity of *Propionibacterium acnes*, and inflammatory responses within the skin.

Hyperpigmentation

Hyperpigmentation is a frequently occurring skin condition in which certain areas of the skin become darker due to excessive melanin synthesis or irregular melanin distribution. Although it can affect people with all skin types, it is more commonly observed in individuals with Fitzpatrick skin types III–VI. Melanin, the natural pigment responsible for skin color, is

produced by melanocytes located in the basal layer of the epidermis and serves as a protective barrier against ultraviolet (UV) radiation. Any imbalance or abnormal regulation in melanin production can result in the development of various hyperpigmentation disorders.

Fig. 2: Acne.

Fig. 3: Hyperpigmentation.

METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Papaya Fruit Extract

Ripe papaya fruits (about 75% ripe, orange in color) were washed properly with clean water, then peeled and the seeds were removed. The fruit pulp was cut into thin slices of around 2–3 mm thickness and dried in a hot air oven at 60°C until completely dry. After drying, the slices were powdered and sieved through a No. 40 mesh to obtain a fine and uniform powder. Around 250 mg of this papaya powder was placed in 1 liter of methanol in a closed container for extraction. The mixture was stirred three times a day and kept for three days (72 hours) for maceration. After the extraction period, the mixture was filtered to collect the liquid extract, while the solid residue was discarded.

Fig. 4: Papaya extract.

Preparation of Butterfly Pea Flower Extract

Fresh flowers of butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) were collected, shade-dried, and stored in an airtight zipper pouch for later use. To prepare the extract, the flowers were first washed with tap water and then with deionized water to remove impurities. After drying, the flowers were crushed into small pieces and sieved through a 120-mesh sieve to obtain a fine powder. About 50 g of this powder was soaked in 500 mL of 98% ethanol for 24 hours using the maceration

method. After extraction, the mixture was filtered to separate the liquid extract. The filtrate was then concentrated using a rotary vacuum evaporator. The final concentrated extract was collected in a sterile container and stored in a refrigerator for further use.

Fig. 5: Butterfly Pea Flower Extract.

Preparation of Liquorice extract

Maceration is a simple extraction method in which plant material (coarse or powdered) is soaked in a closed container with a suitable solvent at room temperature for a specific time. This helps soften and break the plant cells, allowing the active phytochemicals to dissolve into the solvent. The type of solvent used is important because it determines which compounds are extracted. For liquorice root extraction, 10 g of powdered liquorice root was soaked in ethanol and water (30:70 v/v) for 60 minutes to extract glycyrrhizic acid.

Fig. 6: Liquorice extract.

Preparation of Flaxseed Mucilage

Flaxseed mucilage is prepared by soaking 5 g of flaxseeds in 100 mL of distilled water for 4–6 hours. The soaked mixture is then heated at 60–80 °C for 20–30 minutes with continuous stirring to release the mucilage. After cooling, it is filtered through muslin cloth to remove solid particles. The clear filtrate obtained is flaxseed mucilage, which can be used directly or preserved if needed.

Fig. 7: Flaxseed mucilage.

Preparation of Gum Katira

Gum Katira is prepared by slowly adding 3–5 g of Gum Katira to 50–100 mL of distilled water with continuous stirring to avoid lumps. The mixture is soaked for 6–8 hours or overnight at room temperature to allow the gum to swell and form a thick gel. The hydrated mass is then triturated to obtain a smooth mucilage and filtered through muslin cloth to remove impurities. The prepared mucilage is stored in a closed container and preserved if needed.

Fig. 8: Gum katira.

Preparation of Herbal Gel

- Appropriate amounts of gum katira and flaxseed mucilage were selected as gelling agents. Gum katira was initially soaked in distilled water and allowed to swell completely, forming a gel base.
- Flaxseed mucilage was prepared separately by soaking flaxseeds in water, followed by heating and filtration to obtain a thick, viscous extract.
- The swollen gum katira and prepared flaxseed mucilage were then combined with continuous stirring to obtain a uniform gel base.
- Herbal extracts of papaya (*Carica papaya*), licorice (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), and butterfly pea flower (*Clitoria ternatea*) were prepared individually and filtered to ensure clarity.
- These extracts were gradually incorporated into the gel base with gentle mixing to achieve uniform distribution.

- Glycerine was added as a humectant and mixed thoroughly into the formulation.
- Sodium benzoate, dissolved in a small quantity of water, was introduced as a preservative to improve stability.
- Rose water was incorporated to enhance fragrance and impart a soothing effect.
- The formulation was stirred continuously until a smooth, homogeneous, and lump-free gel was formed.
- Finally, the prepared gel was filled into suitable airtight containers and stored at room temperature for further evaluation.

Fig. 9: Herbal Gel containing liquorice, papaya and butterfly pea flower extract.

Table 1: Formulation Design of herbal gel.

S.NO	INGREDIENTS	F1(50ml)	F2(50ml)	F3(50ml)	F4(50ml)
1	Carica papaya extract (Papaya extract)	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
2	Glycyrrhiza glabra L. (Liquorice extract)	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
3	Clitoria ternatea (Butterfly pea flower extract)	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
4	Gum katira	2.5 g	3 g	3.5 g	4 g
5	Linum usitatissimum (Flaxseed mucilage)	8ml	10ml	12ml	14ml
6	Glycerin	5ml	5ml	5ml	5ml
7	Sodium Benzoate	0.2 g	0.2 g	0.2 g	0.2 g
8	Rose Water	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The prepared polyherbal gel formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters to ensure their suitability for topical application.

Physical characteristics: All the formulations showed a smooth, homogeneous appearance with no visible lumps or phase separation. The odor was found to be pleasant and characteristic, mainly due to the presence of rose water, indicating good patient acceptability.

Table 2: Physical characteristics of Herbal Gel Formulations.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4
Colour	violet	Violet	Violet	Violet

Odour	Pleasant and characteristic	Pleasant and characteristic	Pleasant and characteristic	Pleasant and characteristic
Homogeneity	Smooth and free from lumps			

Fig. 10: Physical characteristics of Herbal Gel Formulations.

pH: The pH of all formulations was found within the range of 5.5 to 6.8, which is suitable for skin application. This indicates that the gel is non-irritating and compatible with normal skin pH, reducing the chances of skin irritation.

Table 3: pH Of Herbal Gel Formulations.

Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4
pH	6.0	6.28	6.53	6.06

Fig. 11: pH of Herbal Gel Formulations.

Consistency: All formulations exhibited good consistency with a smooth texture. The gels were neither too thick nor too runny.

Table 4: Consistency of Herbal Gel Formulations.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
Consistency	thick	optimum	slightly thin	runny

Spreadability: The spreadability values were found within the acceptable range (approximately 5-10 g·cm/sec), indicating that the gel can be easily applied on the skin with minimal effort. Good spreadability ensures better patient compliance and uniform application.

Table 5: Spreadability of Herbal Gel Formulations.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
Spreadability	5.8 g.cm/sec	6.5 g.cm /sec	7 g.cm /sec	9 g.cm/sec

Fig. 12: Spreadability of Herbal Gel Formulations.

Irritancy Test: No signs of redness, itching, or irritation were observed during the irritancy study. This confirms that the formulation is safe and non-irritant for topical use.

Table 6: Irritancy Test of Herbal Gel Formulations.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
Irritancy	No	No	No	No

Fig. 13: Skin irritation test of Herbal Gel Formulations.

After-feel and Ease of Removal: The gel exhibited a non-greasy and smooth after-feel, providing a refreshing sensation upon application. It was also found to be easily washable with water, leaving no residue on the skin, except F1.

Table 7: After-feel and Ease of Removal.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
After feel	Smooth, and non sticky	Smooth and non greasy	smooth and Slightly sticky	Smooth and sticky
Ease of removal Or washability	Slightly difficult to remove	Optimum washability	Easily removable	Easily removable

Fig. 14: Ease of removal of Herbal Gel Formulations.

Stability Study: During the stability study, no significant changes in color, odor, pH, or consistency were observed under different storage conditions. This indicates that the formulation is physically and chemically stable.

Table 8: Stability study of Herbal Gel Formulations.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
Stability	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable

Viscosity: The viscosity of the formulations was observed in the range of 5,000–15,000 cP, which is ideal for topical gel formulations. The viscosity was influenced by the concentration of gum katira and flaxseed mucilage.

Table 9: Viscosity of Herbal Gel Formulations.

PARAMETER	F1	F2	F3	F4
Viscosity	14324 cP	12453cP	5241cP	4462 cP

The study successfully formulated polyherbal gels (F1–F4) with good stability, homogeneity, and violet color at pH 6. Variation in gum katira and flaxseed affected viscosity and spreadability. Among all **F2 was the optimized formulation** due to its balanced properties, good spreadability, and pleasant after-feel, making it suitable for topical use.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated polyherbal gel formulations (F1–F4) using natural ingredients and varying concentrations of gum katira and flaxseed gel. All

formulations exhibited good stability, appropriate pH (6), and no signs of irritation, indicating its safety for topical application. The gel comprised Liquorice, papaya extract (*Carica papaya*), butterfly pea flower extract (*Clitoria ternatea*), gum katira (*Astragalus gummifer*), flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimum*), glycerin, sodium benzoate, and rose water. These ingredients are known for their antioxidant, moisturizing, and skin-soothing properties. The different formulations (F1–F4) were evaluated based on various parameters such as viscosity, spreadability, consistency, homogeneity, after-feel, and ease of removal. From the evaluation, it was concluded that **F2 formulation** was the best among all, showing optimal spreadability (6.5 g·cm/sec), viscosity (12453 cps), excellent homogeneity, non-greasy after-feel, and excellent washability. The results demonstrated that the concentration of gum katira significantly influenced the viscosity and consistency of the gel, while flaxseed gel improved spreadability and provided a smoother application. Among all formulations, **F2** was found to be the optimized formulation, as it showed balanced viscosity, good spreadability, smooth texture, non-greasy after-feel, and ease of removal. Therefore, it can be concluded that an effective, stable, and user-friendly polyherbal gel can be developed using natural gelling agents, with **F2** being the **most suitable formulation** for topical application.

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